

DEALING CENTERS IN FOREIGN EXCHANGE MARKET OF UZBEKISTAN: INSTITUTIONAL OR INNOVATIVE PARTICIPANTS

SHAROF RAJABBAEV

Director the Research Center, Tashkent State University of Economics, Tashkent, Uzbekistan

ABSTRACT

The article is devoted to address some specific problems of formation and development of global foreign exchange market. There are determined various factors in formation and development of global foreign exchange markets; critically assessment is given to intermediary role played by dealing centers; reveals the extent of overlooked profits for large institutional participants of financial market of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

KEYWORDS: Foreign Exchange Operations, Institutional Participants, Dealing Centers, Leverage, Trading Platform, Exchange Rate

INTRODUCTION

At present, in national banks of the republic necessary legal and regulatory frameworks and conditions for provision of services for international currency transactions carried out on world foreign exchange markets are created. However, in most cases, this activity remains outside of the focus country's banks. On this occasion there are intermediaries under the appearance of dealing centers in financial markets of Uzbekistan. Thus, potential financial benefits of large institutional participants in financial markets are channeled to dealing centers that pursue goal of fast and easy enrichment. This situation has a negative consequence both for obtaining legal income and investors' protection.

THE ORIGIN OF FOREIGN EXCHANGE MARKET AND INSTITUTIONAL FACTORS IMPACTED ON ITS DEVELOPMENT

Foreign exchange market has deep historical roots. In the works of individual authors, establishment and further development of global foreign exchange market is inextricably linked with adoption of free floating exchange rate regime in 1970 (Cornelius Luca, 1999). However, prerequisites for international exchange transactions were primarily formed in ancient Greece and Rome, where so-called debt notes markets were operated. In the Middle Ages, principal fairs – historical prototypes of global foreign exchange institutions are started operating in Lyon and Antwerp (Rode E, 1986).

Growth and expansion of foreign trade became a driving force for development of money-changing business. In X century, moneychangers (Sarraf) are functioned along the Great Silk Road. Appearance of the first bills in the XVI century in Hamburg and Amsterdam determined institutional importance of banks and consolidated their position as main participants of foreign exchange markets. Further development of the banking system led to adoption of Gold Standard (Epshtein Y, 1913).

After the World War II, the United States' economy became the world's leading economy and, accordingly, national currency of the country has come to play a key role in international financial relations. Since that time, all international trade relations and financial operations are conducted in US dollars. The tendency for accumulation and concentration of financial operations has led to development of individual centers for provision of financial services. Gradually, US dollar started playing the role of dominant reserve currency.

Rapid development of national economies of Germany, Netherlands, France and Japan since 1960 facilitated improvement of export potential of these countries. This factor, among many others, strongly impacted depreciation of US dollar. The US government decided to introduce foreign exchange restrictions in 1970 as an emergency measure to prevent further depreciation of US dollar. This fact contributed to development of Eurocurrency market, which was the next factor that had significant impact on development of foreign exchange transactions by cross transactions in money and foreign exchange markets.

Fixed exchange rate regime functioned during 1945-1970 years within international monetary system framework led to deviation of nominal exchange rate from real exchange rate. In that situation, many countries experienced price parity violations between national and foreign currencies. Exchange rate parity violations contributed to emergence of new participants such as brokers and dealers in global financial markets. Deepening specialization of institutional underpinnings of foreign exchange markets has stimulated accumulation of participants, which paved the way for the emergence of the next factor - development of global financial centers. This factor has set a clear distinction between domestic foreign exchange market, which is subject to national legislation and international foreign exchange market, where there exist codes of conduct for market participants (Klimachev B, 2011).

Initially, balance between supply and demand for capital in real sector of economy formed the price for financial services provided. However, with development and further expansion of globalization processes, the role of speculative financial transactions has increased dramatically. Under such conditions, financial market started to grow strongly, regardless of the needs of the real sector.

Scientific and technological progress, development of communication systems, automation of trade operations and appearance of exchanges with electronic trading in aggregate became a serious factor in the development of globalization processes. Since that time, the globalization processes began to develop both in vertical and horizontal directions. Thus, individual investors have appeared in global financial markets in line with professional financial intermediaries and institutional investors.

If electronic trading systems only began to operate along with traditional trade methods only since 80's of the last century, a decade later, electronic trading systems started being widely implemented in practice. New trading technologies have been introduced particularly in the field of foreign exchange transactions and derivatives. Thus, if in 1995 only 10% of retail foreign exchange transactions conducted through electronic brokerage systems, then by 2013 the total number of transactions has risen to 42%. Initially, derivatives trading was mainly carried out in the form of auctions at London Stock Exchange. However, consequently, this system has been improved and thus, a new electronic trading system Eurex has been created. Well-known term "Forex" previously used in relation to global foreign exchange market has become popular among ordinary citizens of many countries due to increased volume and variety of derivatives transactions, as well as development of electronic trading systems.

Hence, following factors can be attributed as those that determined development of global foreign exchange markets:

- Growth of international trade and its increasing role in economic development;
- Increase in demand for foreign currency in borrowing transactions, development of Eurocurrency market;
- Appearance of risk, associated with unexpected loss or profit as a result of exchange rate fluctuations;
- Concentration of financial resources and development of international financial centers;
- Development of communication systems and automation of trading transactions;
- Development and expansion of derivatives transactions.

INSTITUTIONAL FRAMEWORK OF FOREIGN EXCHANGE MARKET AND THE ROLE OF DEALING CENTERS

Global foreign exchange market has strong institutional framework with commercial banks being at the center (Canales-Kriljenko, Jorge Ivan, 2004). As a rule, all financial transactions are made through banks that provide intermediary services. Demand from customers to buy or sell particular currency is formed as orders that result in open foreign currency position for banks. In order to avoid risks, intermediary banks try to close open foreign exchange position in short period of time, by requesting a reverse order from correspondent banks. If the bank that have received an order from a customer to buy or sell a currency does not close position on time, he takes the risk of incurring loss or gaining profit as a result exchange rate fluctuation.

It should be stated that one needs to have large amounts of funds in order to deal in global foreign exchange markets. At present, some business entities as well as individuals who wish to gain profit from exchange rate fluctuations without having necessary initial funds for making financial transactions at their disposal turned using services of different dealing centers.

In Uzbekistan, dealing centers began to emerge since 2006. They were mostly subsidiaries of Russian dealing centers such as Forex.uz, Forex club, Teletrade, Forex invest, Alpari and others. It is worth mentioning one important detail, notwithstanding that subsidiaries conducted their financial activities on behalf of Russian companies, headquarters, through which financial transactions were carried out were registered in offshore zones.

Dealing centers have become a channel of bypassing authorized banking institutions in making international foreign exchange transactions. Representatives of these dealing centers actively lobbied building public opinion that they are representatives of Forex firms. However, their activity in providing services related to purchase or sale of foreign currency is not legitimate, and pose a great risk.

Intermediary role of dealing centers in financial sector is intrinsically unprofitable for organization itself. Perhaps it is for this very reason, dealing centers providing foreign exchange services to clients tend not to attract too much attention to their services. Hence, established system allows making profits only for those clients who invest small amounts of money. At the same time, clients with relatively large sums might pose risk for operations of dealing centers; therefore become main object of persecution and might lose, as a result.

In order to confuse their client, dealing centers behave in different ways.

It should be noted that financial leverage lies at the heart of dealing centers. In fact, financial leverage is considered to be a high risk activity.

As a rule, in order to attract potential customers, dealing centers offer financial leverages in the following proportions: 1: 100, 1: 500, 1: 1000. The author believes that ratio of financial leverage chosen by a customer determines the extent of risk posed on capital. Newly created dealing centers usually offer the highest ratio. As a rule, such dealing centers are not expected to operate in financial markets for a long period of time. It can be assumed that desire of quick and easy enrichment is the main motive of their actions. Such model of dealing rooms is called - kitchen, where organizer of trading waits for "welding" of a client.

Dealing centers that wish to operate on financial markets for a relatively longer period of time choose more complex models of managing assets. Clearing model is one of them (Figure 1). Dealing centers working through clearing models value their reputation in the market as usually deal with customers having large volumes of capital at their disposal.

Figure 1: Scheme of Dealing Centers Based on Clearing Model

We would like to note the fact that dealing centers will always have tendency to appropriate clients' money regardless of the operating model they choose. We assume that a customer who addressed dealing center may request to return earlier invested and accumulated capital after a certain period of time. In such cases, dealing center operates in this way. If the amount of investment is not very large then the money will be returned to the customer at the expense of new client investments i.e. operate using principles of former pyramids such as MMM (Figure 2). If required amount will be quite large, dealing centers will try to delay the issuance of money using all sorts of ways. Only in most hopeless cases dealing center may declare bankruptcy, close and after some time open up under a brand new name.

Figure 2: Scheme of Dealing Centers Functioning

Another manipulation of dealing centers may have the following form. Dealing center might try to impose all liabilities associated with safety of maintaining current account on the client under terms of financial services provision contract. This point can be specifically prescribed in the contract. This state of affairs might eventually allow dealing center to use embedded client's capital in their own interest in every possible way, and all responsibility for the consequences might be imposed to the client. In many cases, clients of dealing centers are not familiar with entered agreements or do not pay much attention to that specific point, which ultimately would allow dealing centers to rob a depositor. According to current legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan, residents have the right to open a current account in foreign banks only if they have official authorization from the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Therefore, by opening an account in dealing centers, investors evade established order, and as a result, are outside of state guarantee of deposits.

Another opportunity for embezzlement of other people's money emerges because of possibility to control exchange rate. This means that in those cases when there is a situation in which probability of loss increases, dealing centers tend to give false quotations in their own favor, respectively customers having an open position in opposite direction lose money. It is enough to observe quotations given by other brokers in order to identify such actions of dealing centers.

Dealing centers have another solution in case if above mentioned manipulations do not give desired effect and probability of loss for dealing centers increases. This is due to the fact that dealing centers provide services via Internet connection, where it is enough to break down and report that connection to the server is not available («No connection to server»). There is no doubt that after communication recovery exchange rate would be in an unprofitable position for the client. (Khestanov S, 2012)

To sum up, we present general features of dealing centers.

Firstly, they are not financial institutions; as a result, do not affect the state of the market.

Secondly, to cover illegal business activities they try to register in the form of educational or educational-consulting centers.

Third, covert motivation of dealing centers is to promote Forex and to attract depositors to open accounts.

Fourth, dealing centers often use virtual money, in some cases, international plastic cards.

Fifth, bank accounts of dealing centers are located in offshore zones.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Problems that arose in Uzbekistan are not related to Forex system itself or activities of dealing centers. It is mainly due to the fact that banking institutions do not have necessary infrastructure for provision of commercial services on foreign exchange transactions. In any case, current situation in financial sector of our country is compounded by the fact that population is forming not entirely legitimate representation about operation of Forex system. To our view, expanding range of banking services provided for foreign exchange transactions will significantly increase liquidity of domestic foreign exchange market, on the other hand, it will help to raise quality level of foreign exchange transactions to higher position. To realize this strategic line below we will provide necessary measures that should be undertaken.

Firstly, it is necessary to expand correspondent relations of national commercial banks. It is known that establishing correspondent relations is one of the strategic objectives of bank's effective assets and liabilities management. Allocate financial resources in current account in any other bank means to have low-yielding assets. In such circumstances, establishment of Forex operations may bring two-way benefits. On the one hand, at first relatively small banks with access to trading platforms of large banks will be able to create favorable conditions for establishing correspondent relations in the future. Consequently then they will even greater strengthen and expand their relationships. Thus, over time, dividends will be profit of small banks. On the other hand, establishment and further strengthening of correspondent relationships will ultimately help to significantly improve quality of customer services related to cash and settlement operations.

Secondly, each individual bank should develop and implement the use of automated trading platforms which allow conducting financial transactions including Forex operations. It is desirable to have easy-to-use software with compact interface.

Thirdly, taking into account that all financial transactions in Forex are related to leverage, it might be possible to provide financial services in the form of forward exchange transactions and use capital efficiently. In these cases, the use of monetary and exchange rate swap agreements can be used as a short-term financing tool. In such circumstances, investors should be bear in mind that while buying foreign currency over time they will need to sell it back. Making such kind of financial transactions through purchasing foreign currency will temporarily serve as a guarantee for national currency. In addition, developing futures market can lead to greater competition in the spot market. Provision of free access to information on fixed-term contracts ultimately contributes to significant reduction in costs associated with necessity to obtain information about current state of supply and demand for foreign currencies. This fact will have positive impact on situation on domestic financial market, namely free flow of information would deprive privileged status of some market participants thereby creating a more favorable competitive environment. In particular, it can be noted that in case when small and large banks have not equal position in financial market, a change of conditions in futures market will improve competitive environment and give impetus to a new round of development. Summing up above mentioned words, we can conclude that situation in futures market, eventually, may significantly limit monopolistic position of major players, and benefit domestic financial market overall.

Fourthly, in our opinion, determination of exchange rate of national currency based on single foreign currency should be abandoned from common practice even if it is a world currency. In practice, the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan updates exchange rates on weekly basis to maintain accounting records and statistical reports. The Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan does not conduct any operations even with commercial banks of the country based on renewed exchange rates. This in turn complicates the work of commercial banks that miss opportunity of dealing with foreign banks (in other words, opportunity to connect to international information systems...) and thus do not have opportunity to obtain reliable information. Due to the fact that national commercial banks do not have access to essential information, they are obliged to act, at their own risk, relying on exchange rates announced by the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan. In these circumstances, residents of Uzbekistan can potentially become victims of speculations in world financial markets.

National banks that have access to world financial markets are well aware of currency quotes and, therefore, are not tied to information provided by the Central bank of the country.

At the time when the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan officially announces current exchange rate for specific foreign currency, it is quite fair that the practice of limiting the use of exchange rates by other commercial banks that significantly varies from official exchange rate (with a possible margin of up to 2%) causes discontent of International Monetary Fund (IMF) officials. Taking this into consideration we think that it would be reasonable if the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan will put into practice the principle of quoting foreign exchange rates directly from world foreign exchange markets. In practice, this would mean official abandonment of exchange rate determination based on cross-rate. Fifthly, to our view, the practice of mandatory reserves for foreign currencies by the country's commercial banks should be abandoned. It is known that mandatory reserve requirement for foreign currency is a special tool of monetary policy of the Central Bank. Nevertheless, since foreign currency is a part of money supply of another country it cannot be manipulated by monetary policy of the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Abandoning the principle of mandatory reserve requirements for foreign currency deposits, in market conditions, will significantly increase interest rates on deposits. Moreover, abandonment of mandatory reserve requirement for foreign currency deposits will positively impact development of futures market. As forward position opened by bank will give an opportunity to invest the same amount of money supply in financial market and thereby avoid risks associated with foreign exchange movements.

CONCLUSIONS

Deficit of highly qualified personnel knowing peculiarities of working in financial and foreign exchange markets, lack of essential information about foreign exchange market and insufficient practice in these financial markets altogether make this form of activity quite risky. Elimination of above mentioned problems will eventually allow to significantly increase national banks' revenues. Furthermore, there will be significant increase in domestic foreign exchange market liquidity, chances for guaranteed protection of local investors' interests will rise, it will be realistically possible to limit detrimental influence of offshore areas on national economy, and there will be an opportunity to significantly improve foreign exchange market infrastructure. Overall, all above mentioned benefits of these transformations will create favorable environment for successful integration of country's financial system into global financial system.

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